

Job Satisfaction And Employee Performance In Private Universities In Anambra State, Nigeria

¹Onya, Chinwe Caroline; ²Dr Arinze, Stephen Emeka & ³Dr. Chidi Leonard Atueyi

¹Department of Business Administration
Federal polytechnic Oko, Anambra State, Nigeria

²Department of Business Administration
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Igbariam, Anambra State, Nigeria

³Department of Economics
Legacy University Okija, Anambra State Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The study examined job satisfaction and employee's performance among the staff of private universities in Anambra state. The study investigated the relationship between reward, career development, staff training and recognition on employee performance. Relevant theoretical and empirical literatures were reviewed. The study was anchored on Herzberg's theory. The study collected data from primary and secondary sources. The population of the study comprised 478 staff of private universities in Anambra state. Formulated hypothesis were tested, using ANOVA. From the analysis, it was discovered that: Reward has significant effect on employee's performance amongst the staff of private universities in Anambra state. Career advancement has significant effect on employee's performance, amongst the staff of private universities in Anambra state. Training has significant effect on employees' performance amongst the staff of private universities in Anambra state. In view of the findings, The study also recommended that management should provide effective incentive plan to their employees from time to time to boost their morale for enhanced productivity and performance. The reason is that bonuses will encourage them to put more effort in discharging their duties effectively. Employees should be trained according to the present content of the environment. The reason is that training implies acquiring knowledge to fill the gap between what is known and what should be known. Therefore, seminars/workshop should be regularly organized by the management in order to update the employee knowledge

Keywords: job satisfaction, employee's performance, reward, career development, staff training, recognition and employee performance

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The history of job satisfaction research began in the 1930s. Early definitions described job satisfaction as a combination of psychological, physiological, and environmental factors that lead a person to say they are satisfied with their job. One of the biggest influences was the Hawthorne studies in the 1920s-1930s, which showed that novel changes temporarily increase productivity due to being observed, not the changes themselves (Oguntayo Unegbu & Alegbeleye, 2024). This provided evidence that factors other than pay influence job satisfaction. Scientific management also impacted the field by increasing

productivity but leaving workers exhausted and dissatisfied. Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory, proposing that people seek to satisfy physiological, safety, social, esteem, and self-actualization needs, provided a foundation for early job satisfaction theories. (Ogbonnaya, Gambo and Abubakar 2024)

Record has shown that It is a general understanding that job satisfaction is an attitude towards job. In other words job satisfaction is an affective or emotional response toward various facets of one's job (Emeka, 2022). A person with a high level of job satisfaction holds positive attitudes towards his or her job, while a person who is dissatisfied with his or her job holds negative attitudes about the job (Smerek, & Peterson, 2022). Job satisfaction is a result of employees' perception of how well their job provides those things which are viewed as important. Job satisfaction is also defined as reintegration of effects produced by individual's perception of fulfillment of his needs in relation to his work and the surrounding (Hussaini, Waziri, & Bukar, 2024).

Organizations can achieve strategic goals through workforce efforts. It is widely believed that employees are the company's most valuable assets (Ilagan & Javier, 2014). Javier (2011), emphasized that the key to business success is its ability to retain the loyalty of its stakeholders, which include not only their customers but also the employees who run the business activities. Organization's performance depends among others the contribution of its workforce and this has bearing with employee job satisfaction. Satisfied employees create and deliver value out of other organizational resources. Employee job satisfaction has being interconnected with how people think, feel and observe their jobs (Emeka 2021)

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Employee job satisfaction is very important to the workforce in any organization. Statistics has shown that employee performance is also critical factor to organizational performance. However, negative work incentives (such as poor reward system, lack of career development, lack of training on the part of employees and no organizational structure put in place to encourage recognition of employees) make work boring, dissatisfying and this in turn, is a major problem that can affect employee performance. This negative work incentives lead to increased absenteeism, turnover and accidents. Thus to prevent these negative work outcomes, there is a need to find out which factors within the organizational context which can lead to satisfaction among staff of private universities in Anambra State, so as to, continually have productive, satisfied and contented employees.

Some organizations shy away from ensuring employee job satisfaction and this may likely be due to cost implications. Most of the private staff of the private universities sell, hawk, and even scramble for contracts and supplies when they are supposed to be in their offices. The individuals whose goals and aspirations are thwarted by the organization becomes frustrated, develop feelings of low self-worth, become apathetic, disinterested and tend to withdraw self commitment in their work. Personal business outside the organization becomes more important. The unsatisfied worker may be physically present at their place of work, but his mind and thought are off the job. There is no doubt that if public servants have job satisfaction, they will perform better in their job, the research will therefore examine the effect of job satisfaction on employee's performance among the staff of private universities in Anambra State.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study is to examine the job satisfaction and employees performance of private universities in Anambra State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. Determine the effect of reward system on employees' performance amongst the staff of the private universities in Anambra State.
2. Examine the effect of career advancement on employees' performance amongst the staff of the private universities in Anambra State.
3. Evaluate the effect of training on employees' performance amongst the staff of private universities in Anambra State.
4. Examine the effect of staff recognition on employees' performance amongst the staff of private universities in Anambra State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1. Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Job Satisfaction

The concept of job satisfaction has a strong psychological underpinning and traditionally has been of great interest to social scientists concerned with the problems of work in a business practitioners. The concept itself, over the years has transformed to become a Nobel area of research in understanding human motivation (Bosede, 2024). Job satisfaction as concept has been widely researched especially in the area of management and organizational behaviour. However, general perspective on the concept of job satisfaction exists with different interpretation but mostly defined along the line of aspects of an individual job and employee well-being. Taken into consideration of previous studies, it is observed that institutional concept of job satisfaction describing employees working attitudes in an effort to conceptualize job satisfaction has gradually evolved over time (Gitonga, Egessa, & Tibbs, 2024).

2.1.2 Employee Performance

Employee performance or job performance as interchangeably used is a multi-dimensional construct because employee performance is determined by more than one kind of behaviour (Mawoli & Babandako, 2011), and influenced by lots of determinants (Alromaihi, Alshomaly & George, 2017). According to Armstrong and Taylor (2014) employee performance as a multi-dimensional concept consisting of two aspect namely the behavioural which entails the process and the outcome that entails the result aspect. Sonnetag, Volmer and Spsychala (2008) described behavioural aspect as what people do at work while the outcome aspect refers to the results of the individual behaviours. Similarly, Robbins and Judge (2013) opined that three major types of behaviour constitute employee performance namely: task performance, citizenship and counter-productive performance. This study adopts this proposition to conceptualize employee performance (i.e, task performance, citizenship and counter-productive performance) to form conceptual framework (Jacobs, & Arinze, 2021).

2.1.3 Reward

Reward exists in order to motivate employees to work towards achieving strategic goals which are set by the entities. Armstrong (as cited in Anku, Amewugach & Glover 2018) ‘ ‘ reward systems consist of the interested processes and practices which combine to ensure that the reward management is carried out effectively to the benefit of the organization and the people who work there’ ’ it is based on the reward strategy, which are derived from business strategy. These strategy coordinates and controls the operation and advancement of reward practices, process and thus, shape policies that involves reward management which in turn influence reward practices, process and procedures (Anku, et al 2018)

2.1.4 Career Development

Career development is perceived like joint effort between the individual employee and the organization. Career development describes the lifelong process of managing life, learning and work. It involves individuals planning and making decisions about education, training and career choices as well as developing the right skills and knowledge to do this (Arthur et al, 2015). Greenhaus et al, (2015) sought to investigate the relationship between talent management and succession planning processes. The study, which was carried out using descriptive and inferential statistics revealed that talent management and succession planning within government organizations met the requirements and therefore impacted on talent absorption, talent retention and talent development which gave the organizations a competitive edge.

2.1.5 Staff Training

Training and development is a form of non-financial reward (intrinsic) which is designed to improve a person's skill to perform specific tasks or duties more effectively. It is designed to improve an employees' skill to perform a current job, Ngige (2011). He further observed that, even if an individual knows well as how to perform a particular job, through training and development, his skills and abilities could be further refined to enable him perform the job in a better manner. In the same view, development refers to the process of education and developing selected personnel so that they have the knowledge and skills needed to manage in future positions, Werther and Davies (2016).

2.1.6 Recognition

Recognition is a process of giving an employee certain status within an organization. This is very crucial as it motivates an employee towards greater achievements, enhances the career advancements and impact on organizational growth and survival. Recognition describes how the work of an employee is evaluated and how much the appreciation the employee receives in return from the organization. Also, it specifies the way an organization gives its employees the reward and status for his works and activities. Organizations in today's complex and competitive environment are always on the look out to find out the relationship and reasonable balance between employee satisfaction and performance of the organization as it relates to its survival and growth. The reward and recognition programs serve as the most crucial factor in keeping employees' passionate and career advancement high.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory Herzberg's theory is said to be the most functional model to study job satisfaction (Kim, 2004). The two factor theory suggests that there are two factors that could satisfy or dissatisfy workers in carrying out their responsibilities namely job-satisfiers or motivator factors and job dissatisfaction or hygiene factors. Job-satisfier are aspects of the features of a job including skill variety, task identity, task significance and autonomy as factors that affect individual's perception of how important the work is, and eventually affects satisfaction level. Autonomy represents the level of exercising self-control, the more independent a worker feels, the more responsibilities he or she assumes. Hygiene factors (security, status, supervision etc) were characterized a lower level motivators. Where they have not been satisfied, job dissatisfaction is the result.

Relevance of the theory to the Study

The research conducted by Hertzberg determined what people actually want from their jobs. The respondents had to describe work situations in which they felt good(satisfied) or bad (dissatisfied) in their jobs. The feedback received was then categorized into satisfaction or dissatisfaction. The characteristics related to job satisfaction included advancement, recognition, the work itself, achievement, growth and responsibilities. Hertzberg referred to these characteristics as „motivators“. The characteristics related to dissatisfaction, which included working conditions, supervision, interpersonal relationships, company policy and administration were referred to as „hygiene“ factors (Robbins, 2001).

According to Schermerhorn (1993), Herzberg's two-factor theory is an important frame of reference for managers who want to gain an understanding of job satisfaction and related job performance issues. Schermerhorn asserts that Herzberg's two-factor theory is a useful reminder that there are two important aspects of all jobs: what people do in terms of job tasks (job content), and the work setting in which they do it (job context). Schermerhorn suggests that managers should attempt to always eliminate poor hygiene sources of job dissatisfaction in the workplace and ensure building satisfier factors into job content to maximize opportunities for job satisfaction. This theory is relevant and significant to this study in that it recognizes that employees have two categories of needs that operate in them and that both should be addressed. This theory therefore can guide a researcher in establishing determinants of employees' satisfaction in private universities in Nigeria.

2.3 Empirical Review

Ikhenoba & Imoh-Ita. (2024). investigated job satisfaction amongst employees of Esit Eket Local Government Council and its relationship with their performance. Using a survey research method, the researchers administered a questionnaire to the entire staff population of 256, of which 246 representing 96.09% were correctly completed and returned. The findings of the study revealed that there is job satisfaction amongst the workers as evidenced by the low staff turnover and exit rate from the sector and that there is a significant relationship between Local Government employee job satisfaction and performance. To sustain and increase the satisfaction level, the study recommended that the government should carry out innovative improvements to the working conditions of staff at Esit Eket in a way that is enriching and gives room for value creation, such that innovation and creativity now attract key rewards such as promotion, to sustain staff satisfaction

Agubosim, Arshad, Alias, & Moosavi, (2023) the study examines the Job Satisfaction and Job Performance among University Staff in Nigeria. This study was conducted using qualitative research

methods based on case studies and using the intrinsic and extrinsic factors of job satisfaction as the context for the collection of research data. A total of 20 staffs were interviewed consisting of Store's Manager, Communications Director, Technical Officer, Librarian, Audit officer, Transport Manager, Security officer, Public relations officer, 2 Information Technology officer's, Accountant, Graphic designer, Front desk executive, Personal assistant to the Head of department (marketing), Secretary (school of marketing), procurement officer, Administrative assistant, Secretary in Assistant registrar's office, Administrative secretary, and Photographer. Data were collected through in-depth semi-structured interviews supported by relevant information from participant observation, document analysis and field notes. The data was then analyzed and given codes, categories and sub-themes to develop main themes to answer each research question. In conclusion, job satisfaction among staffs can help increase performance of staffs.

Fatma, Latif, Wijaya, Nilasari, & Nisfiannoor, (2023). influence of the Work Environment, Rewards, Organizational Culture on Employee Performance which is mediated by Job Satisfaction. The data used in this research is primary data taken by distributing questionnaires using a purposive sampling method involving 190 frontliner employees of state-owned banks in South Jakarta, Indonesia. The analytical tool in this study is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) using AMOS version 24. The results of this study are that there is a positive and significant effect of work environment and rewards on job satisfaction, but organizational culture has no effect on job satisfaction, there is a positive and significant effect work environment and job satisfaction on employee performance, but rewards and organizational culture have no effect on employee performance. There is a positive and significant effect of work environment and rewards on employee performance through the mediation of job satisfaction. However, organizational culture has no effect on employee performance through the mediation of job satisfaction..

Atueyi (2019) examined the effect of external debt and human capital development in Nigeria. Three research objectives were formulated. Ex-post facto research design was adopted and time series data spanning 32 years (1986-2017) were processed using the models earlier formulated. Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression technique was used to analyze the data. Secondary sources of data were applied and sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin, the variables were on human capital index, debt servicing, gross fixed capital formation and external debt. Unit root test, co-integration approach, error correction model, causality test and stability were employed to analyze the included variables. The study found that external debt has a negative and significant effect on human capital development in Nigeria, debt financing has a negative insignificant effect on human capital development, and lastly gross fixed capital formation has positive insignificant effect on human capital development.

Ifechukwu-jacobs, C.J & Atueyi, C.L (2025). Material management and productivity of Nigeria bottling appraised the material management and productivity of Nigerian Bottling Company. The study adopted survey method of research. Data were generated through primary and secondary sources. The method for data collection was questionnaire which was administered randomly among the staff of Nigerian Bottling Company. The population of the study was 288 staff. while two hundred and seventy (270) questionnaires were retrieved. The hypotheses were tested using regression analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed, Planning has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha given its F-value of 14.027. Material procurement has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha given its F-value of 33.048. Logistic has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha given its F-value of 9.418. Stock and waste control has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha.

Manafa, Okeke & Atueyi (2022). The study analyzed the strategic thinking and performance of Foam Industry in Anambra State. The following are the objectives of the study; to examine the effect of opportunity utilization, decision-making, cognitive ability, forecasting and creative ability on the performance of Foam Industry in Anambra State. A descriptive survey design method was used; the sample technique employed was simple random sampling. ANOVA method of data analysis was used. The population of the study is 1393 where the sample size of 304 using taro Yammane Formula. The researcher administered 304 questionnaires but only 302 were retrieved and used for the analysis. Structured questionnaires were used to gather information from the population. The study found that,

Opportunity utilization has significant positive relationship with the performance of Foam Industry in Anambra State.

Ntadom Atueyi & Jacobs (2021) examined the effect of career development on organizational performance, a Study of selected higher institution in Anambra State Nigeria. The study was anchored on Self-concept theory of career development. As a cross-sectional survey the research design were used, a structured questionnaire instrument were developed and used for data collection by the researcher to which reflect such options as strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree, which is popularly referred as five (5) points likert scale. It was used to obtain information from the respondents. The population of the study comprised of 57, 710 students selected across the five south east states of Nigeria. A sample size of 399 students was drawn from the population, using Taro Yamane formular of which three hundred and fortyseven (347) copies of questionnaires were duly completed and returned; showing 96% response rate. Research hypotheses were tested using ANOVA regression analysis which was carried out with the aid of Statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 23. The study found that career development has significant effect on Organizational Performance.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study adopted the descriptive survey design using the primary data collection method. With the aid of a structured close ended questionnaire on a five point Likert scale as the instrument for data collection, the researcher distributed the copies of the questionnaire to respondents in the selected study area. (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2009).

3.2 Area of the study

The study was carried out in all the private universities in Anambra State of Nigeria. Anambra State is located in the south-east of Nigeria and is among the thirty six state of the federation. It shares a common boundary with Delta State to the west, Imo State in the south, Enugu State in the East and Kogi state in the North. The state is sub-divided into three senatorial zones which are AnambraNorth, Anambra Central and Anambra South. It has 21 local government areas with 177 communities. The state has two public universities and four private universities recognized by the National Universities Commission. The people of the area are predominantly Igbos and they also speak Igbo as their major language. The citizens of Anambra State are variously traders, artisans, farmers and civil servants. The state has its headquarters at Awka.

3.3 Population of the Study

The population of study was made up of employees (lecturers) of the private universities in Anambra State. Therefore, the population of the study is four hundred and seventy-eight (478) employees. Since the population is not up to one thousand, the researcher will used the entire population as the sample size

s/n	Universities	Staff Strength	Location
1	Tansian University	134	Umunya
2	Legacy University	78	OKija
3	Paul University	109	Awka
4	Madonna University	157	Okija
	Total	478	

Source: Wages and Salaries Department of the Respective Institutions

3.4 Sources of Data

In this study we used both primary and secondary data.

Sources of data

The data will be obtained from two sources namely: primary and secondary sources

a. Primary Sources of data

The primary data was generated from private universities staff using a structured questionnaire.

b. Secondary Sources of data

Secondary data was collected from published sources (annual reports, handbook and pamphlets)

Information from the internet, books, newspapers, journals/magazines, etc are of great help.

3.5 Method of data collection

The instrument that was employed for data collection is questionnaire designed by the researcher. The instrument consists of two parts. Part 1 gathered demographic information about the respondents. Part 2 of the instrument is a 5-point Likert scale instrument. The scale will consist of 5 options ranging from 5(Strongly Agree), 4(Agree), 3(Undecided) 2(Strongly Disagree), 1(Disagree). The questionnaire was close-ended in nature, designed to elicit information on the effect of job satisfaction on employee's performance among the staff of private universities in Anambra state.

3.6 Validity of Instrument

The study used face and content validity,. The drafted instrument was first given to three lecturers in Business Administration department in Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus for validation, before it was given to the supervisor for face validity. Their corrections and suggestions were incorporated into the final draft of the questionnaire. The questionnaire is attached in appendix.

3.7: Reliability Test of Instrument

Reliability of the research instrument simply means the idea that another researcher would obtain the same findings if the study were repeated. In other words reliability is the degree to which the instruments are error free and thus yield consistent results. The reliability of the instrument was maintained through the test-retest method. The pretest was conducted with (10) copies of the questionnaire administered to ten (10) respondents at two points in time (one week interval). The responses of number of respondents that strongly agreed or agreed were collated and scores correlated using the spearman's rank correlation of coefficient. The coefficient of reliability was found to be high, $R_s=0.79394$. This indicates a strong and positive correlation therefore, the research instrument was adjudged as being reliable.

3.8 Method of Data Analysis

Statistics, including frequency count, tables and percentages was put to use in the analysis of personal characteristics and data analysis, while research hypotheses was tested using multiple regression analysis. The research hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Analysis was carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), (Version 23).

DATA PRESENTAION AND ANALYSIS

This chapter presents the data obtained from the respondents through the administered questionnaire. Four hundred and seventy-eight (478) copies of the questionnaire were administered, to the selected staff. However, three hundred and seventy-seven (377) copies were retrieved which 79%. Therefore the analysis and interpretation of data were only based on the returned copies of the questionnaires. The validity and reliability of this study is highly ensured, despite the number of copies not returned. However the first instrument, which is demographic characteristics has to with bio-data of the respondent, while the second Instrument, tagged, Analysis, which is showing options such as A, SA, D, SD, U shows analysis and opinion of the respondents.

4.1 Demographic characteristics of Respondent

4.1.1 Sex

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	MALE	273	71.3	72.4
	FEMALE	104	27.2	27.6
	Total	377	98.4	100.0

Source: SPSS Version 21, 2025

The above table reveals that two hundred and seventy-three (273) of the respondents, which represents 72.4%, were male, while one hundred and four (104) respondents, which represent 27.2%, were female,. By implication, male respondents were more than female respondents by 44.8% in our selected

population sample for this study. The implication of this is to enable us to know the number of female and male that successfully returned their questionnaire

4.1.2 Category Of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SENIOR STAFF	248	64.8	65.8
	JUNIOR STAFF	129	33.7	34.2
	Total	377	98.4	100.0

Source: SPSS Version 21, 2025

The above table reveals that the two hundred and forty-eight (248) of the respondents which represents 65.8% were senior staff, while one hundred and twenty-nine (129) respondents which represent 34.2% were junior staff. By implication, senior staff were more than junior staff in our selected population sample for this study. The implication of this is to enable us to know the category of the respondents that successfully returned their questionnaire.

4.1.3 Education Qualification Of The Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	OND/NCE	174	45.4	46.2
	B.SC/HND	167	43.6	44.3
	MSC/MBA	13	3.4	3.4
	PHD	17	4.4	4.5
	OTHERS	6	1.6	1.6
	Total	377	98.4	100.0

Source: SPSS Version 21, 2025

In the table above, out of the three hundred and seventy-seven (377) respondents, one hundred and seventy-four (174) of the respondents are OND/NCE holders. While one hundred and sixty-seven (167) respondents which represent 44.3 percent are BSC/HND holders. Thirteen respondents (13) which represent 3.4 are MSC/MBA holders, while seventeen (17) which represents 4.5 are PHD holders. Lastly, six (6) which represents 1.6 answered others.

4.1.4 Age Bracket Of The Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-25 YEARS	68	17.8	18.0
	26-35 YEARS	127	33.2	33.7
	36-45 YEARS	152	39.7	40.3
	46-ABOVE	30	7.8	8.0
	Total	377	98.4	100.0

Source: SPSS Version 21, 2025

The table above shows that respondents whose age bracket falls between 18-25 yrs were sixty-eight (68) which represent 18 percent. This is followed by those with age bracket of 26-35 years with one hundred and twenty-seven (127) which represents 33.7%. Also those within age bracket of 36-45yrs were one hundred and fifty-two (152) which represents 40.3%. Lastly, those with age bracket of 46-above with thirty respondents which represent 8%. The implication of this age distribution is to enable us to check if the questionnaire was directed to the right age group

4.1.5 Work Experience Of The Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	BELOW 5 YEARS	153	39.9	40.6
	6-10	191	49.9	50.7
	11-20 YEARS	17	4.4	4.5
	21 YEARS AND ABOVE	16	4.2	4.2
	Total	377	98.4	100.0

Source: SPSS Version 21, 2025

The table above shows that one hundred and fifty-three respondents which represent 40.6 percent have work experience below five years; one hundred and ninety-one (191) which represents 50.7% have work experience of 6-10yrs. Again, seventeen respondents (17) which represent 4.5% have work experience of 11-20yrs. Lastly, sixteen respondents (16) which represent 4.2% have work experience of 21yrs-above.

4.2 Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One

H0: Reward has no significant effect on employees’ performance amongst the staff of private universities in Anambra state.

Table 4.3.1 ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6.911	2	1.382	7.613	.000 ^b
	Residual	80.589	375	3.358		
	Total	87.500	377			

Source: SPSS, Version, 20 2025

However, from the Anova table above, it was observed that the probability value of hypothesis one is less than 0.05% level of significance (0.000), as a result null hypothesis was rejected and alternative is accepted, Reward has significant effect on employees’ performance amongst the staff of private universities in Anambra state

Hypothesis Two

H0: Career advancement has no significant effect on employees’ performance, amongst the staff of private universities in Anambra state.

Table 4.3.2 ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	22.507	2	4.501	6.952	.002 ^b
	Residual	64.993	375	2.708		
	Total	87.500	377			

Source: SPSS, Version, 20 2025

However, from the Anova table above, it was observed that the probability value of hypothesis two is less than 0.05% level of significance (0.002), as a result null hypothesis was rejected and alternative accepted, meanwhile. Career advancement has significant effect on employees’ performance, amongst the staff of private universities in Anambra state.

4.3.3 Hypothesis Three

H0: Training has no significant effect on employees’ performance amongst the staff of private universities in Anambra state.

4.4.3 ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	881.762	2	25.193	213.295	.000
Within Groups	3.511	375	3.511		
Total	885.274	377			

Source: SPSS, Version, 20 2025

The test conducted revealed that the large significance value (F.sig<.002) indicate no group differences. Since the F-value of 213.295 with a significance of .002 is less than .05 (i.e .002<.05), training has significant effect on employees’ performance amongst the staff of private universities in Anambra state.

4.3.4 Hypothesis Four

H0: Recognition has no significant effect on employees’ performance amongst he staff of private universities in Anambra state

ANOVA

Table 4.3.4

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.746	2	.373	7.286	.002
Within Groups	161.869	375	1.305		
Total	162.614	377			

Sources: SPSS Output 2025

The test conducted revealed that the large significance value (F.sig<.002) indicate no group differences. Since the F-value of 7.286 with a significance of .002 is less than .05 (i.e .002<.05), Recognition has significant effect on employees’ performance amongst he staff of private universities in Anambra state

4.4 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This research examined the effect of job satisfaction on employees’ performance among the staff of private universities in Anambra state. Data were sourced from the employee of the selected staff in the private universities in Anambra state. The data generated were subjected to statistical analysis and the following output was ascertained.

Reward and Employee Performance: The study found that Reward has a significant positive effect on employee performance in the private universities in Anambra state. The implication of these findings is that, for reward system to be functional to achieve their aim and purposes, the salaries need to satisfy the expected needs of the individual, and must be seen to be fair or equitably satisfying to the employee. This further agreed with the findings of Iyida (2015), who found that increase in reward enhances the productivity of workers. The findings also corroborate with the findings of Olatunji and Sarat (2014) that salaries are pertinent determinant to employee motivation and performance in Nigeria.

Career Development on Employee Performance: The study found that career development had significant positive effect on employee performance of private universities in Anambra state. The implication of these findings is that, for career development to be functional to achieve their aim and purposes, the career development need to satisfy the expected needs of the individual, and must be seen to be fair or equitably satisfying to the employee. This further agreed with the findings of Iyida (2015), who found that increase in career development enhances the productivity of workers. The findings also corroborate with the findings of Olatunji and Sarat (2014) that career development is a pertinent determinant to Performance in Nigeria.

Training and Employee Performance: The study found that training had a significant positive effect on Productivity of employee performance in private universities in Anambra state. This implies that Productivity provide motivation and propel employees to behave in ways that would lead to enhanced productivity. Alfandi and Alkawsawneh (2014) found that enriched Productivity is a significant factor that encourages employees as well as increase their zeal at work which results in enhanced Productivity and employee performance. The Productivity may include multiple benefits and perks other than financial gains. Employees with high job satisfaction tend to exert higher levels of performance, productivity, commitment and retention rates

Staff Recognition and Employee Performance: The study found that staff recognition has a significant positive effect on employee performance private universities in Anambra state. The implication is that acknowledgement of staff for good performance and obedience to the rules and policies of the long term goals reinforce particular behavior and commitment that would lead to better performance and positive result. The finding is in line with the study of Aamir, Syad, Abdul, Quasim and Shahzad (2019) that Staff recognition play an important role in boosting employee commitment performance and enhance over all organization performance. This also agrees with the study of Hatice (2012) that intrinsic reward can significantly influence the performance of individual employee positively

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Summary of the Study

This study examined the effect of job satisfaction on employees' performance among the staff of private universities in Anambra state. The study concludes that the independent variable has a positive influence on dependent variable of performance Thus, there is no doubt that job satisfaction has a powerful impact on the performance of an organization and its ability to implement the programs and agendas of the organization which they serve. The following are the findings of the study.

- i. Reward has significant effect on employee's performance among the staff of private universities in Anambra state
- ii. Career advancement has significant effect on employee's performance, among the private universities in Anambra state
- iii Training has significant effect on employees' performance among the staff of private universities in Anambra state
- iv Recognition has significant effect on employees' performance among the staff of private universities in Anambra state

5.2 Conclusion

The study focused on the impact of job satisfaction on employee's performance among the staff of private universities in Anambra state. The study concludes that reward, carrier development training, productivity as well as recognition have positive effect on employee performance but such effect is strong and statistically significant. Their coefficients are statistically different from zero at less than 5 percent level of significance. It is obvious to reward, carrier development, productivity as well as recognition are sine qua non for stimulating worker's performance in any organization. When rewards are not given, workers tend to express their displeasure through poor performance and non-commitment to their job. It is therefore, important for any organization to consider the needs and feelings of its employees and not just overlook them because "a happy worker they say is a productive worker.' The study concludes that, job satisfaction has significant positive effect on employee job/task performance in the private universities in Anambra state, Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

In line with the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The study also recommends that management should provide effective reward plan to their employees from time to time to boost their morale for enhanced productivity and performance. The reason is that rewards will encourage them to put more effort in discharging their duties effectively.

2. Career advancement programs in universities should be used as a knowledge retention tool by management to significantly channel efforts in a way that will drive organization to build adaptive capability
3. Identification of training requirements should be done in collaboration with line managers and those responsible to improve human resources. Everyone engaged should agree on the specific shortcomings of the staff. For example, what skills are required and what attitudes toward performance must be altered
4. Management should give out recognition bonuses to its outstanding teams as well as individuals to enhance motivation using items such as plaques, gift cards, jewelry and on the spot cast awards.

REFERENCES

- Agubosim, B. B., Arshad, M. M., Alias, S. N., & Moosavi, A. (2023). Job Satisfaction and Job Performance among University Staff in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 12(2), 2620–2631.
- Alromaihi, M. A., Alshomaly, Z. A., & George, S. (2017). Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance: A Theoretical Review of the Relationship between the two Variables. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences*, 6(1), 1–20.
- Armstrong, M., & Taylor, S. (2014). *Armstrong's Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice* (13th Ed.). London: Michael Armstrong
- Arthur, M. B., (2015). "Examining contemporary careers: a call for interdisciplinary inquiry." *Journal of Human Relations*, 61, (2), pp. 163-86.
- Atueyi C. L. (2019). External debt on human capital development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Economics*, 7 (1) 49-58
- Bosede, O. D. A. (2024). Employee Well Being and Organizational Performance of Private Universities in South-South, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Education and Sustainable Development*. 4(4), 47-64.
- Emeka S. A (2022) effect of succession planning on sustainability of family businesses in Anambra and Lagos States Of Southern Nigeria. *International Journal of Business Systems and Economics* 13 (5) 51 – 63
- Emeka S. A. (2021) *Performance appraisal and employee performance: A Study of Selected Banks in Awka Anambra State, Nigeria.* *International Journal of Business Systems and Economics*, 13 (4) 27 – 52
- Fatma, K., Latif , M., Wijaya, M. H., Nilasari , B. M., & Nisfiannoor , M. (2023). The Effect of Work Environment, Reward, and Organization Culture on Employee Performance Through Job Satisfaction as Intervening Variables. *Archives of Business Research*, 11(1), 68–84.
- Gitonga, C.K, Egessa, R & Tibbs, C (2024). Effect of career development on talent engagement in selected private technical and vocational education training institutions in Kenya, 5 (4) 1252 - 1265
- Greenhaus, J.G., Callanan, G.A., & Godshalk, V.M. (2015). *Career management*. (3rd ed.). New York: The Dryden Press
- Hussaini, A.M Waziri, A.U & Bukar, k (2024). effect of job satisfaction on the performance of academic staff of the university of Maiduguri, Borno State. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 11 (1) 400 – 412
- Ifechukwu-jacobs, C.J & Atueyi, C.L (2024) Material management and productivity of nigeria bottling company Onitsha Anambra State. *International Journal of Economics, Finance & Entrepreneurship*,9 (8) 17-32
- Ikhenoba, W & Imoh-Ita. I (2024). Job Satisfaction and Staff Performance in Esit Eket Local Government Council of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *AKSU Journal of Administration and Corporate Governance*, 4 (1) 122-136

- Ilagan, J. L. T., Javier, F. V. (2014). Supervision and other determinants of employee morale: the case of banco de oro Branches in Batangas City and Bauan, Philippines, *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(5), 138-149
- Jacobs, C.J & Arinze, E.S (2021). effect of team work on organizational performance: a study of Cosharis Rice Mill Igbariam *African Journal of Business and Economic Development* 1 (10) 74-86
- Javier, E.R. (2011). Organizational spirituality and people management practices of selected banks in Batangas City: Measures Towards Management Effectiveness. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(1): 336-355
- Manafa, G.U, Okeke O.C & Atueyi C. L (2022). Strategic Thinking and Performance of Foam Industry In Anambra State. *African Journal of Business and Economic Development | ISSN: 2782-7658 Vol. 2, Issue 4 (April, 2022) | www.ijaar.org*
- Ngige C.D (2011) *Human Res. Mgt*, Enugu, Holy ghost cathedral: social common
- Ntadom G. U. Atueyi C.L. & Jacobs C. J.(2021). effect of career development on organizational performance a study of selected higher institution in Anambra State Nigeria. *International Journal of Business & Law Research* 9(2):1-10,
- Oguntayo S. A., Unegbu V. E., & Alegbeleye, G. O. (2024). analysis of professional competencies and job satisfaction of librarians in private universities in south-west, Nigeria. *Fudma Journal Of Sciences*, 7(6), 382 - 390.
- Robbins, S., & Judge, T. (2013). *Organizational Behaviour*(15th Ed.
- Smerek, R. E., & Peterson, M. (2017). Examining herzberg's theory: improving job satisfaction among Non-Academic Employees at University. *Research in Higher Education*, 48(2), 229–250.
- Sonnentag, S., Volmer, J., & Spsychala, A. (2008). *Job Performance*. (B.Julian, Ed.). SAGE
- Wether, S, & Pavies, A, (2016). "The Impact of person organization fit on job satisfaction and performance of the employees," *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 11, (2014) 122 – 129